

Speculation of Role of $dS=0$ for Directional/Dynamical Quantum Probability $\exp(ipx)$

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. April 24, 2024

In (1) we suggested that quantum mechanics is associated with a dynamical probability $\exp(ipx)$ (generalized momentum * spatial variable) for the case in which the generalized momentum is conserved i.e. the spatial variable is invariant with respect to p . We suggested that such a dynamical probability is required to solve dynamical probabilistic problems such as one dimensional reflection-refraction. Even in such a case, one requires two equations. One matches dynamical probabilities at the interface x point, and the other momentum multiplied by this probability (i.e. the first derivative) at the same x . Here, we suggest that one may create a Shannon's entropy from $\exp(ipx)$ and use this to justify the first derivative matching at the interface. To do so, we use $dS=dS/dx dx =0$ (for all three pieces: incident, reflected and refracted), i.e. one uses additive entropy to obtain the first derivative continuity equation.

We then try to extend the idea of $dS=0$ to average information values. For example, a particle in a square well or infinite well may be described by average momenta. We suggest that this average momentum is information and that $\exp(ip(\text{ave}) \text{ generalized space variable})$ is still probability or even $\exp(-ip(\text{ave}) \text{ space variable})$ outside of well. In such a case, we argue that one may use $dS=0$ for this average momentum to justify a derivative d/dx continuity equation at the well boundary.

Dynamical/directional Probability and Specific and Average Momentum

We suggested in (1) that given a constant momentum in one direction, one may create a directional probability:

$$\exp(ipx) \quad ((1))$$

This dynamical (complex) probability has two immediate features, the first is:

$$\ln(\exp(ipx)) = ipx = \text{information and } d/dx \ln(\exp(ipx)) = p \text{ information} \quad ((2))$$

and the second: $\exp(-ipx) \exp(ipx) = 1 \quad ((3))$

The value of 1 in ((3)) is linked with $P(x)=\text{constant}$ in classical physics.

Next imagine that one has an unbiased region of space with an average momentum, $p(\text{ave})$. In such a case, one should have $p(\text{ave})$ for the particles moving forward and $-p(\text{ave})$ for the particles moving backwards. Classically, $P(x)dx = dx/L$ ($L=\text{length}$) and one should be able to write:

$$\exp(ip(\text{ave}) x) \text{ for the dynamical average probability} \quad ((4))$$

Thus, the same form holds for p or p_{ave} for a dynamical probability in the case of spatial invariance in a region of space.

We next consider creating Shannon's entropy for both p and p_{ave} cases and argue that $dS=0$ accounts for equating first derivatives of $\exp(ipx)$ s at an interface point.

The Case of One Dimensional Reflection and Refraction

Consider a photon moving in a vacuum along the x axis (to the right) and hitting an interface with n_2 (index of refraction) at $x=0$. Using dynamical probabilities, one may match dynamical probability and average momentum at $x=0$. Another way to view this is to state that the dynamical probability and its first derivative are continuous at $x=0$. This leads to:

$$A \exp(ipx) \text{ at } x=0 + B \exp(-ipx) \text{ at } x=0 = C \exp(ip_2 x) \text{ where } p_2 = pn_2 \quad ((5a))$$

$$Ap - pB = Cp_2 \quad ((5b))$$

One may use ((5a)) and ((5b)) to solve for B/A and C/A .

We next suggest that ((5b)) is equivalent to $dS=0$, where S is Shannon's entropy for the dynamical probability $\exp(ipx)$. Thus, the continuity of the first derivative seems to take on a thermodynamic meaning. Here entropy is essentially being used like a information weighted by a probability (rather than $\ln(\text{number of states})$).

First we note that if one changes the interface by dx , then x increases by dx on the LHS and decreases by $-dx$ on the RHS. Thus, using:

$$S = A \exp(ipx) \ln(A \exp(ipx)) = ipxA \exp(ipx) + \ln A \quad ((6))$$

and assuming additivity of entropies, one may write:

$$dS/dx \, dx = ipx \exp(ipx) A (dx) + B (-ipx) \exp(-ipx) (dx) + C (ip_2 x) (-dx) \exp(ip_2 x) = 0 \quad ((7))$$

Canceling out dx and x and then setting $x=0$, one has:

$$Ap - Bp = C p_2 \quad ((8))$$

Thus, we suggest that a continuous derivative is equivalent to $dS=dS/dx \, dx = 0$ at a junction point. This has been applied to specific p values.

The Case of P average

We next consider the use of $dS=dS/dx \, dx = 0$ as applied to an average momentum. We consider the example of a quantum particle in a well. In this situation, one has $p(\text{ave})$ inside the well (which is a translationally invariant region. Inside the well, $k = \sqrt{E + |V|}$), but E is negative

from the Schrodinger equation, i.e. represents binding energy. Here $-V$ is the value of the negative potential. Outside the potential, one should have $\exp(ipx)$ s because the particle is free at least for a very tiny distance, but overall (on average) it is not because of interactions. If one uses a complex momentum because E is negative in this region for E being constant in all space, then one has $\exp(ipave x) \rightarrow \exp(-Kx)$ outside the well, but we suggest that this is an average value.

Usually (2) one matches dynamical probability and its first derivative at a box wall. If the wall is at $-a$ and $+a$ and one considers even parity at $x=0$, then inside the box one has $A \cos(pave x)$ where $pave$ is proportional to $\sqrt{E+V}$. An odd parity solution is $A \sin(pave x)$.

For the odd parity case with $pave=k$.

$A \cos(pave a) = C \exp(-Ka)$ ((9a)) and $A pave \sin(pave a) = CK \exp(-Ka)$ ((9b)) or

$K = k \tan(ka)$ ((10)) A similar result may be found for the even parity solution.

Here we suggest that ((9a)) may be obtained using $dS=dS/dx dx=0$. If one moves the right wall by dx , then x increases by (dx) for A inside, but decreases for the region outside the well. Thus:

$$dS=dS/dx dx = -A pave \sin(pave a) (dx) + C (-dx) K \exp(-Ka) = 0$$

This may be combined with a probability continuity equation at $x=a$, to obtain ((10)).

Thus, we suggest that $dS=0$, a thermodynamical result, may physically account for the mathematical process of equating derivatives d/dx at a junction point.

Conclusion

In a previous note (1), we suggested that one may create a dynamical probability $\exp(ipx)$ for a constant p (momentum). This probability is closely related to the information ipx . In this note, we suggest that if one has a translationally invariant region with a $pave$, one may use $\exp(ipave x)$ to describe it. We then consider Shannon's entropy as a property of a dynamical variable and apply it to the case of one dimensional reflection/refraction. Using $dS=dS/dx dx=0$ and noting that if one moves the interface to the right, dx increases for the incident and reflected rays, but decreases for the refracted, one may obtain the continuity of d/dx . Thus, we suggest that the mathematical d/dx continuity equation has an underlying thermodynamical physical meaning, namely $dS=0$.

We apply the same $dS=0$ approach to a p (average) scenario, i.e. a quantum particle in a well.

In such a case, we extend $\exp(ipx)$ to $\exp(ipave x)$ for the case of $pave$ being purely complex outside the well. It is still a linear combination of $\exp(ipx)$ s in this region, we argue. Using $dS=0$, one may again obtain a continuity of d/dx equation at the well wall which may be combined with a dynamical probability continuity at the wall..

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco Directional Probability in the Macroscopic World and Quantum Mechanics (preprint, zenodo, 2024)
2. *Jim Branson 2013-04-22 U. of California San Diego*
https://quantummechanics.ucsd.edu/ph130a/130_notes/node151.html